

THEORIES ON THE STATE AND DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE IN THE REPUBLIC

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Abstract. It serves to ensure food security while increasing the economic efficiency of agriculture. It is achieved through the rational use of existing labor, land, water, material and financial resources, regardless of the forms of ownership, based on the improvement of economic relations between them.

Key words: economic efficiency, profit, material cost, income, cultivated area, gross product, yield, net profit, cotton fiber, financial resources.

Based on the opinions and opinions of scientists who have conducted research on the methodology of economic efficiency evaluation until now, they can be conditionally divided into two groups. Scientists belonging to the first group believe that the criterion indicator of economic efficiency should be the only one. According to them, this indicator has a general characteristic and should objectively and completely reflect the economic efficiency. The second group of economists advocates that economic efficiency should be determined through a system of indicators.

From this point of view, in researching the issues of development of cotton production, all economists put forward their scientifically based opinions and opinions, based on the period of studying the problems in this field and the forms of economic management.

The cotton complex occupies an important place in the process of socio-economic development, and it is of great importance for the economy of the country, which dominates its successful development. Cotton products processed in factories are very important raw materials for the light and food industry. Cotton products are also used in heavy industry. Up to 300 types of consumer products and technical products are made from cotton raw materials. In the economy of our country, the weight of cotton growing and cotton ginning industry is large. As the industry develops, other sectors of the national economy will also develop. From this point of view, further development of cotton growing is considered one of the priorities of our republic. It is known that our country has long been famous for its climate, senmiun soil, underground and surface resources.

The achievements in the development of cotton cultivation in Uzbekistan until now depended on a number of unique factors. Therefore, studying the history of the development of cotton in our country from the point of view of the factors that affect it allows to theoretically justify the historical improvement of the factors that affect the development of the industry. Cotton has been grown in Uzbekistan for more than 2500 years. The reason is that the natural and climatic conditions of our country have been favorable for growing cotton since ancient times. The free trade of cotton fiber on the world market and the increase in demand for it has led to an increase in the volume of cotton production and the attraction of a

large amount of resources to this sector. During the past period in Uzbekistan, the volume of raw cotton production has also changed with the change of cotton cultivation areas.

Uzbekistan was transformed into the cotton raw material base of the former union, cotton was planted on its main arable fields, and this period was rightly called the period of "cotton monopoly" in the history of cotton production. At this stage, the development of cotton farming was carried out mainly at the expense of mechanization and chemicalization of the industry, and issues such as increasing soil fertility and farming culture, compliance with ecological requirements, material interests of cotton growers and their social condition were second only to the issue of increasing cotton raw materials.

Mustaqillik yillarigacha paxtachilikni rivojlantirishning ekstensiv usuli mumkin bo'lgan yagona usul bo'lib hisoblandi. Paxtachilikni ekstensiv usulda rivojlanishining tabiiyligi shundaki, o'tgan davr mobaynida O'zbekistonda qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishida foydalanilmayotgan erlar yetarli miqdorda mavjud edi. Bu usulning yagonaligi shundaki, paxtachilikda uzoq yillar davomida bir xildagi takomillashmagan ishlab chiqarish vositalaridan va oddiy texnologiyalardan foydalanish bilan cheklanib kelindi.

The issues of developing the cotton industry and increasing its economic efficiency are to a certain extent related to the laws that are being formed in the countries that grow and consume cotton. Because the main categories that determine the price of cotton fiber in the world market, not taking into account supply and demand can have a negative impact on the development of the industry. Taking into account the demand and supply of cotton fiber in the world market, firstly, it allows to clearly define the cultivated areas necessary for cotton production, and secondly, based on the practice of the countries of the world, cotton production, domestic consumption and export in the cotton sector of our country provides an opportunity to develop scientifically based ratios that are compatible with the state's level of development according to its indicators. Taking into account the ratio of supply and demand, determining the size of cotton cultivation areas on a scientific basis ensures the flexibility of cotton growers to the market.

It is important to take into account the unique characteristics of the network in the development of cotton. These features establish some of the features that distinguish cotton farming from other industries. Including:

- that the development of cotton production is a priority in meeting the demand of industrial enterprises for raw materials and solving social problems;
- making raw materials grown in the cotton industry suitable for consumption by members of society requires several stages of processing;
- that cotton growers do not have the opportunity to satisfy their consumption requirements of a certain form with the intermediate finished product (producers of vegetables, grain, livestock products can use the finished product for personal consumption without any further processing);
- that the production of raw cotton is an industry that requires regular regulation by labor and economic means, etc.

Increasing labor productivity is important for network development and economic efficiency. Labor productivity in cotton farming is the process of reducing the labor costs required to produce a unit of output and is based on:

- financial stability of cotton farms;
- the existence of an effective material-technical and services market;

- level of network mechanization;
- product production in accordance with demand and supply;
- less use of live labor, etc.

In the conditions where the laws of market relations apply, the main goal of cotton growers is to get more income, and they choose the most convenient and effective way to achieve their goals. Ultimately, the chosen path creates the formation of labor productivity in different ways. If there is cheap labor in the network, the level of their use will be high and will justify the tendency of labor productivity to decrease, and the cheapness of the services of technical means will justify the tendency of labor productivity to grow in the cotton industry. So, achieving labor productivity in cotton farming is the basis for the formation of the following positive aspects in the industry:

- reduction of labor costs, effective use of land, water, and material resources;
- achieving an intensive increase in the volume of raw cotton;
- decrease in product cost and increase in income;
- increasing the material interests of cotton growers, etc.

The issue of supply of material and technical resources in cotton farming is considered to be one of the factors that have a strong impact on the development of the industry, and in the conditions of transition to market relations, their purchase prices are required to be proportional to the purchase prices of the raw materials being produced. On the contrary, the disparity between the prices of the material and technical resources produced in the industry and used in cotton production and the purchase price of cotton raw materials causes the price of cotton to rise, and this situation can have a serious negative impact on the economic efficiency of cotton production. However, the economic efficiency of cotton farming depends not only on the prices of material and technical means, but also on their effective use. Failure to carry out agrotechnical activities on time due to non-effective use of material and technical means causes a decrease in soil fertility and a decrease in cotton yield.

Social factors affecting network development are directly related to ownership relations. Adjustment of ownership and use of property in cotton farming to the requirements of market relations, in turn, leads to improvement of the relations of cotton growers to property and labor. On this basis, it is necessary to improve the material benefit system in the formation of agrarian relations in cotton farming. This is the main requirement of the market economy based on social relations. The implementation of this goal will depend on the improvement of the legal and regulatory documents in force in the network. From this point of view, it is an objective necessity to determine the goals and tasks of the legal and regulatory documents adopted and applied in connection with the organization and development of cotton production based on the requirements of the market economy based on social relations.

References:

1. Murtazaev O. Problems of increasing the efficiency of the cotton agro-industrial complex. T.: Science, 2005.
2. Farmanov T.Kh. Prospects for the development of farms. — T.: New age generation, 2004.
3. Husanov R.H. The main essence of the new technology in the cultivation of cotton raw materials. — T.: Labor, -1993.

4. Sh.A. Yuldasheva "Factors of increasing economic efficiency in cotton farming" (on the example of agrocluster "Sakhib Omad Barakasi" LLC in Izboskan district) written for the master's academic degree – 2022
5. Nafasova, D. (2022). TABIIY RESURSLARNI BOSHQARISH, EKOLOGIYA VA ATROF-MUHIT MUHOFAZASI. Scientific progress, 3(3), 739-744.
6. Турсунов, Х., & Алибаев, М. А. (2020). Важность обеспечения безопасности наземных транспортных средств. Life Sciences and Agriculture, (3-2), 33-36.
7. Hamdam, T. (2022). Theoretical and Methodological Aspects of Community Supervision Instituting. American Journal of Economics and Business Management, 5(9), 80-85.
8. Tursunov, X. T., & Rahimova, T. U. (2006). Ekologiya.
9. Турсунов, Х., & Алибаев, М. А. (2020). REQUIREMENTS TO ENSURE THE SAFETY OF GROUND VEHICLES. Life Sciences and Agriculture, (3-2), 33-36.
10. Турсунов, Х. КОРХОНАЛАРДА МЕХНАТНИ МУХОФАЗА КИЛИШНИ АСОСИЙ ЧОРА-ТАДБИРЛАРИ ВА УНИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШДА КАСАБА УЮШМАЛАРИНИНГ РОЛИ. Хорижий hamkorlar ishtirokida o 'tkazilgan Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani to'plamining TAHRIR XAY'NATI, 607.
11. Habibullaevna, K. C., & Hamdam, T. . (2023). Training of the Population in the Field of Civil Defense and Protection against Emergencies. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(3), 17–20.
12. Abdurashid, A. (2023). SANOAT KORXONALARIDA YUK KO'TARISH MASHINALARINI ISHLATISH TARTIBI VA XAVFSIZ ISHLATISH BO'YICHA CHORA-TADBIRLAR ISHLAB CHIQISH. Journal of new century innovations, 24(3), 46-50.
13. Abdurashid, A., & qizi Xushvaqтова, V. A. (2023). ISH JOYLARIDAGI JAROHATLANISHLARNI OLDINI OLISH BO'YICHA XALQARO TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI. Journal of new century innovations, 23(3), 173-176.
14. Abduraxmonov, A. A., & Dadabayeva, N. A. (2021). O'TA XAVFLI YUQUMLI KASALLIKLAR VA ULARNING TARQALISHINI OLDINI OLISH CHORA TADBIRLARI. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(3), 340-351.
15. Atakhanovich, Abdurakhmonov A., and Dadaboeva N. Abdurazakovna. "Origin And Protection Of Epidemiological And Episootic Diseases." JournalNX, 2021, pp. 744-751.
16. Abdurakhmonov, A. A., & Dadabayeva, N. A. PREVENT SERIOUS INFECTIOUS DISEASES AND THEIR SPREAD PRECAUTIONARY MEASURES.
17. Abdurashid, A. (2023). Energetik innovatsion poligon tashkil etish. Journal of new century innovations, 20(1), 169-177.
18. Abdurashid, A. (2023). Qayta tiklanuvchi energetika manbai. Journal of new century innovations, 20(1), 178-186.
19. Абдурахмонов А. А., Дадабаева Н. А. ЗАМОНАВИЙ РАҚАМЛИ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИНГ ҚЎЛЛАНИЛИШ СОҲАЛАРИ ВА ЮТУҚЛАРИ //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т.
20. Abdurakhmanov, A., & Usmonov, U. (2023, January). THE PROBLEMS OF AUTOMOBILE ENTERPRISE STUDYING MUD SWEATS AND STORING THEM IN A LAND. In Proceedings of International Conference on Scientific Research in Natural and Social Sciences (Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 105-108).

21. ATAXANOV, R. (2021). FARGONA VODIYSI QORAKALPOGLARY ZAMONAVIY KIIYIMLARIDAGI ANANAVIY ZHIHATLAR. www.fdu.uz. _
22. ATAXANOV, R. (2022). Chorvador khalqlar ananaviy moddiy madaniyatining airim zhihatlari (Fargona vodiysi korakalpoqlarining ananaviy taomlariga oid materiallarr tahlili) .
23. Atakhanov, R. S. (2021). Karakalpakhs of the fergana valley: migration and integration processes. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(5), 586-596.
24. Sotvoldievich, A. R. (2021). Farg'ona vodiysi qoraqalpoqlarida oilaga oid an'ana va marosimlar: An'ana va zamonaviylik. *Web of Scientist: Xalqaro ilmiy tadqiqot jurnali* , 2 (05), 747-755.
25. Атаханов, Р. С., & Ахунов, М. А. (2023). КАРАКАЛПАКЫ ФЕРГАНЫ: В ПРОШЛОМ И НАСТОЯЩЕМ (анализ полевых исследований). *Journal of new century innovations*, 12(1), 82-90.
26. Sotvoldiyevich, A. R. (2021). Dafn marosimi bilan bog'liq oilaviy marosimlar (Farg'ona vodiysi qoraqalpoqlari misolida). *Berlin tadqiqotlari Transmilliy fan va gumanitar fanlar jurnali* , 1 (1,5 Pedagogika fanlari).
27. Атаханов, Р. С. (2023, March). ФАРФОНА ВОДИЙСИ ПОЛИЭТНИК ТАРКИБИНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШИДА МИГРАЦИЯ ЖАРАЁНЛАРИНИНГ ТАЪСИРИ. In *Proceedings of International Educators Conference (Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 27-31)*.
28. Атаханов, Р. С. (2023, March). ТРАДИЦИОННОЕ ХОЗЯЙСТВО КАРАКАЛПАКОВ ФЕРГАНСКОЙ ДОЛИНЫ. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies (Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 105-109)*.
29. ATAXANOV, R. (2023). FARGONA VODIYSI POLIETNIK TARKIBINING SHAKLLANISHIDA MIGRATION ZHARAYONLARINING TASIRI.
30. Атаханов, Р. (2022). МАТЕРИАЛЫ К ИССЛЕДОВАНИЮ ПОХОРОННО-ПОМИНАЛЬНОЙ ОБРЯДНОСТИ КАРАКАЛПАКОВ ФЕРГАНЫ: ТРАДИЦИИ И ИННОВАЦИИ (НА ОСНОВЕ ПОЛЕВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ). *Вестник Ошского государственного педагогического университета имени А. Мырсабекова*, 2(2), 24-31.
31. ATAXANOV, R. (2022). QORAQALPOQ FARG'ONASI DANOS VA JANOS MARASYONLARINI O'RGANISH UCHUN MATERIALLAR: urf-odatlar va yangilanishlar (DALA TADQIQOTLARI ASOSIDA). O'sh davlat pedagogika universiteti .
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.56122/..v2i2.18>
32. Sotvoldievich, A. R. (2022). TRADITIONAL FISHING ACTIVITIES OF KARAKALPAKS IN FERGANA VALLEY (Field Ethnographic Data Analysis). *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 3, 246-249.

